

Synthesis and mesophase characterization of novel 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)-pyridine derivatives as discotic liquid crystals

Yuvaraju Kanithi*, Abdul Rajack, Y. Varapasab and Y. L. N. Murthy

Organic Research Labs, Andhra Univerisity, Visakhapatnam-530 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : yuva.kanithi@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 26 December 2013, accepted 28 February 2014

Abstract : Synthesis of novel 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridines and the structure was confirmed by ¹H NMR, UV, MS spectral data, their liquid crystalline properties were determined by polarizing optical microscopy, differential scanning calorimetry and X-ray diffraction studies. These 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine derivatives were found to exhibit hexagonal columnar mesomorphism over a wide temperature range.

Keywords : Discotic liquid crystal (DLC), differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), polarising microscope (PM), X-ray diffraction, columnar phase.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been considerable attention in the development of molecular electronics. In this regard, discotic liquid crystals (DLCs) play an important role due to their unique optical¹ and non-linear properties². DLCs exhibiting discotic nematic phase³⁻⁵ are potential candidates to be used in optical compensation films to enhance the viewing angle capability⁶. Also, the hierarchical self-assembly of DLCs and their supramolecular columnar architecture are of fundamental importance not only as models for one dimensional transportation of charge, ion and energy but also as functional materials for the enhancement of properties through formation of self-organised mono domain on macroscopic scales⁷. For example, excellent charge transports through columns were achieved for π -conjugated DLCs⁷⁻¹⁵. In addition, due to their high charge carrier mobility⁸⁻¹⁵, self healing of defects^{16,17}, defect free long-range order and tendency to form highly ordered films of various thicknesses¹⁸, these materials can be regarded as potential candidates for a number of molecular electronic devices. But, for all the device applications, columnar liquid crystals with an appropriate chemical structure and morphology are required. The main prerequisite for an efficient engineering and processing of a columnar liquid crystal by either thermal processing^{19,20} or solution processing^{21,22} in the form of

devices is the presence of desired properties like appropriate thermal behaviour and solubility¹⁹⁻²². Additionally, the operating temperature for all these devices is usually at room temperature. So, it is highly important to obtain materials with good intermolecular interactions and packing at ambient conditions.

In order to achieve this apposite isotropisation as well as melting temperature, various methods have been suggested in the literature, which include branching²³⁻²⁵, unsaturation²⁴, hetero atom substitution²⁶⁻²⁸ etc. Assorted examples in the literature have shown the effect of branching on melting and isotropic temperatures. Among them, the use of branched alkyl chains to tune the mesophase behaviour of various liquid crystal (LC) materials has been well documented in the literature. With the view to study and characterize novel crystals, it is to proposed to synthesize novel liquid crystals and further characterize their liquid crystal properties. 2,4,6-Tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridines are expected to be potential for this study. Hence in this present investigation, we report synthesis of 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridines and the structure was confirmed by spectral data. All the newly synthesized compounds exhibited liquid crystalline properties. The mesomorphic properties of long chain substituted hetero aromatic compounds were examined by polarizing microscope equipped with hot stage and also by differential

scanning calorimeter (DSC data). The observed textures were photographed and the respective thermograms were recorded at the rate of heating 10 °C/min.

Experimental

Synthesis : To a mixture of *p*-hydroxyacetophenone (**1**) (4 mmol) and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (**2**) (2 mmol) and (NH₄)₂CO₃ (4 mmol) was refluxed in water for 6 h at 150 °C under sealed conditions (seal tube). After the completion of reaction the reaction mixture is cooled to room temperature and poured in crushed ice, yellow colour 2,4,6-tri(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)pyridine²⁹⁻³¹ (**3**) yield (93–98%) is obtained as a crystalline solid (Scheme 1) which is further purified by column chromatography and the purity was checked by TLC and HPLC, m.p. >300 °C above.

The structure of compound (**3**) was confirmed by its IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, Mass spectral technique; IR (ν_{max}, KBr) : 3472, 1600, 1583, 1472, 1440, 1204, 1162, 1125, 925, 763, 677; ¹H NMR (DMSO/TMS, 90 MHz) :

6.84–6.94 (6H, d), 7.76–8.15 (8H, m), 9.80 (1H, brs); ¹³C NMR (DMSO/TMS, 22.5 MHz) : 113.5, 115.5, 115.9, 128.3, 128.7, 130.3, 144.9, 149.0, 156.3, 158.2. Mass ion (*m/z*) : 370.1 [M⁺].

Compound (**3**) on reaction with long chain fatty acid chloride (RCOCl, R = undecyl, lauryl, stearyl, palmityl) in DMAP and dichloromethane at reflux temperature yielded 2,4,6-tris(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine derivatives (**5-8**). The synthetic route is shown in Scheme 1. All the esters were purified by column chromatography with *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent. These products were recrystallized from methanol and purity of these above esters were checked by TLC and HPLC (99%).

Synthesis of 2,4,6-tri(*p*-palmitoyloxyphenyl)pyridine (7**) :** 2,4,6-Tri(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)pyridine (**3**) and palmitoyl chloride (prepared by action of SOCl₂ in palmitic acid and palmitoyl chloride thus prepared was distilled at reduced pressure) were refluxed in the presence of DMAP in DCM for 5–6 h. After usual workup, it yields a crude ester.

- RCOCl, **5** = CH₃(CH₂)₉COCl
6 = CH₃(CH₂)₁₀COCl
7 = CH₃(CH₂)₁₄COCl
8 = CH₃(CH₂)₁₆COCl

Scheme 1

Purification of the crude ester over a column of silica gel eluting with *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) afforded 2,4,6-tri(*p*-palmitoyloxyphenyl)pyridine (**7**). Purity of this compound was checked by TLC and HPLC.

The structure of compound (**7**) was confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and Mass spectral data were recorded. IR (ν_{max} KBr) : 2959, 2918, 2840, 1757, 1702, 1588, 1513, 1409, 1117, 931, 719). The ¹H NMR spectrum and ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound (**7**) were recorded. ¹H NMR (DMSO+CDCl₃/TMS, 400 MHz) : 0.8–0.9 (methyl, s), 1.2–1.5 (-CH₂-, s), 2.1–2.3 (-COCH₂-, t), 7.0–7.1 (aromatic protons), 7.9–8.1 (aromatic protons); ¹³C NMR (DMSO+CDCl₃/TMS, 100 MHz) : 12.4, 20.8, 23.1, 27.3, 27.4, 27.6, 27.7, 30.0, 32.4, 114.5, 115.0, 115.8, 128.8, 151.9, 159.4, 173.4. Mass ion (*m/z*) : 1069 (M⁺).

Based on the above spectral data the compound (**7**) was confirmed as 2,4,6-tri (*p*-palmitoyloxyphenyl)pyridine. The thermographic liquid crystal behavior of the compound (**7**) was evaluated by differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) and polarizing microscope.

Differential scanning calorimeter study :

The differential scanning calorimetric data was recorded on DSC Q2000 V 24.9 Built 121 instrument at IIT, Hyderabad, India and Aurabindo Labs, Hyderabad.

Compound (**7**) 10 mg, dried completely was placed in a aluminum sample pan and sealed. The compound was studied for differential scanning calorimetric data at a heating rate 10 °C/min up to 250 °C and on cooling also. The DSC thermogram for compound (**7**) was recorded on cooling from isotropic to mesophase. Compound (**7**) exhibited mesophase between the temperature 41.46–54.0 °C and enthalpy (ΔH) 60.22 j/g. The phase transition temperature and the enthalpy (ΔH) were recorded and presented in Fig. 1.

In order to further confirm the mesophase, compound (**7**) was studied using polarizing microscope on slow cooling from isotropic liquid state, texture³³ (a texture typical that of a hexagonal columnar mesophase) was observed during the mesophase. The observed texture was presented in Fig. 2.

Similarly compounds (**5**, **6**, **8**) were synthesized and characterized by spectroscopic data and the spectral data

Fig. 1. DSC thermogram of compound (**7**) on cooling.

Fig. 2. Texture photography during the mesophase region of compound (7) (A texture typical that of hexagonal columnar mesophase)³³.

was recorded in Table 1. HPLC purity and retention times were recorded in Table 2. The DSC thermogram for compound (5) was recorded on cooling from isotropic to mesophase. Compound (5) exhibited mesophase between the temperature 53.33–68.00 °C and enthalpy (ΔH) 26.10 j/g. The phase transition temperature and the enthalpy (ΔH) were recorded and presented. In order to further confirm the mesophase, compound (5) was studied using polarizing microscope on slow cooling from isotropic liq-

uid state, texture was observed during the mesophase. The DSC thermogram for compound (6) was recorded on cooling from isotropic to mesophase. Compound (6) exhibited mesophase between the temperature 41.98–52.00 °C and enthalpy (ΔH) 123.10 j/g. In order to further confirm the mesophase, compound (6) was studied using polarizing microscope on slow cooling from isotropic liquid state, texture was observed during the mesophase. The DSC thermogram for Compound (8) was

Table 1. Spectral data of 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine derivatives (5–8)

Compd.	IR spectral data (cm^{-1})	^1H NMR spectral data (δ ppm)	^{13}C NMR spectral data (δ ppm)	Mass ion (m/z)
5	2954, 2916, 2849, 1754, 1700, 1605, 1593, 1472, 1247, 1166, 1145, 924, 763	0.8–0.9 (9H, s), 1.2–1.5 (48H, m), 2.2–2.3 (6H, s), 7.1–7.2 (6H, d), 7.5–7.8 (6H, aromatic)	13.95, 22.4, 24.6, 28.8, 29.03, 29.09, 29.4, 31.6, 34.1, 116.4, 121.7, 122.2, 127.9, 128.0, 136.5, 151.4, 156.2, 171.9	
6	2954, 2918, 2845, 1754, 1702, 1676, 1598, 1515, 1293, 1215, 936, 832	0.8–0.9 (9H, s), 1.2–1.6 (54H, m), 2.2–2.3 (6H, s), 7.0–7.1 (6H, d), 7.6–7.9 (8H, aromatic)	13.8, 22.3, 24.6, 28.8, 28.9, 29.1, 29.2, 31.5, 33.9, 115.3, 115.7, 116.2, 128.4, 128.8, 153.2, 159.3, 175.3	
7	2959, 2918, 2840, 1757, 1702, 1588, 1513, 1409, 1117, 931, 719	0.8–0.9 (9H, s), 1.3–1.6 (78H, s), 2.1–2.2 (6H, s), 7.0–7.1 (6H, d), 7.9–8.1 (8H, aromatic)	12.4, 20.8, 23.1, 27.3, 27.4, 27.6, 27.7, 30.0, 32.4, 114.5, 115.0, 115.8, 128.8, 151.9, 159.4, 173.4	1069
8	2954, 2918, 2818, 1759, 1702, 1603, 1547, 1505, 1420, 1200, 1164, 926, 838, 724	0.8–0.9 (9H, s), 1.2–1.8 (90H, s), 2.5–2.7 (6H, s), 7.2–8.2 (14H, aromatic)	13.4, 21.9, 24.1, 28.5, 28.7, 28.9, 31.1, 33.6, 111.0, 121.2, 121.7, 127.4, 127.5, 135.4, 148.0, 150.0, 155.0, 171.4	

Table 2. Retention time and percentage of purity of 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine esters (**5-8**)

Sr. No.	Compd.	Retention time (min)	Purity (%)
1.	5	3.434	98.5
2.	6	3.56	98.7
3.	7	3.388	98.26
4.	8	3.536	98.2

HPLC experimental conditions : Mobile phase : acetonitrile, Column : silica column, Flow rate : 1 ml/min, Detector : UV (254 nm), Injected quantity : 10 μ L.

recorded on cooling from isotropic to mesophase. Compound (**8**) exhibited two mesophses, one mesophase was in between the temperature 56.0–71.0 °C and enthalpy (ΔH) 149.3 j/g and the second mesophase was in between 138.35–161.0 °C and enthalpy (ΔH) 12.7 j/g.

In order to further confirm the mesophase, compound (**8**) was studied using polarizing microscope on slow cooling from isotropic liquid state, a road like texture was observed during the mesophase. DSC thermographic data i.e. phase transition temperature and enthalpy (ΔH) were recorded for the above esters (**5-8**) in Table 3.

Characterization of the discotic mesophase :

After a thorough study of the thermograms and the textures we extended our studies to confirm the columnar phase of the above new synthesized liquid crystals by X-ray diffraction study.

X-Ray diffraction study : In our investigations the X-ray diffraction pattern of the 2,4,6-tri(*p*-palmitoyloxyphenyl)pyridine³² (**7**), the existence of the mesophase as a hexagonal columnar (Col_h) phase was confirmed by XRD. XRD data was recorded at Advanced Analytical Laboratory, Instrument Facility, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam. The diffraction pattern for compound (**7**) was recorded at room temperature to confirm the colum-

nar phase of compound (**7**). XRD pattern of compound (**7**) was presented in Fig. 3, in which 2 θ profile on X-axis versus one dimensional intensity on Y-axis was recorded. In the small angle region, three sharp peaks were observed, the observed peaks are in ascending order of diffraction angle. The *d*-spacing values of first three intensive peaks of were 17.9 Å, 10.01 Å and 8.6 Å respectively. The *d*-spacing of the first reflection (lowest angle and highest intensity) to the other two, was in the ratio 1 : 1/ $\sqrt{3}$: 1/2. These values correspond to that expected from a two dimensional hexagonal lattice. In the wide angle region, there were two diffused peaks; a broad one at 19.8° and another sharp peak at higher angles. The broad peak with a *d*-spacing of 4.4 Å was due to the liquid-like packing of the aliphatic chains. The relatively narrow peak, which was separated from the broader one, corresponds to a spacing of 3.56 Å and was due to core-to-core (intra columnar) separation. All the features confirm the hexagonal columnar (Col_h) phase, in which the disc-like molecules stack one on top of another to form columns, and the columns in turn, are arranged in a two-dimensional hexagonal lattice.

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffraction pattern of 2,4,6-tri(*p*-palmitoyloxyphenyl)pyridine (**7**).

Table 3. DSC thermographic data of compounds **5** to **8** (DSC Q2000 V24.9 Build 121)

Compd.	Temperature in °C	Enthalpy (ΔH)	Temperature in °C	Enthalpy (ΔH)
	crystal (K)–mesophase (S ₁)	K–S ₁ (j/mg)	S ₁ –isotropic	S ₁ –I (j/mg)
5	53.33–68.00	26.10 j/g	–	–
6	41.98–52.00	123.10 j/g	–	–
7	41.46–54.00	60.22 j/g	–	–
8	56.0–71.00	149.30 j/g	138.35–161.00	12.70 j/g

Results and discussion

From the literature survey we examined that liquid crystal properties of 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine derivatives which are not reported earlier by any research group. Hence we synthesized 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine esters. 2,4,6-Tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine esters (Scheme 1) and the structure was confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and its Mass spectral data. The newly synthesized compounds were examined for liquid crystal properties. During the course of our studies on thermotropic liquid crystals of hetero aromatic compounds, it is observed that 2,4,6-tri(*p*-stearoyloxyphenyl)pyridine display mesophase on wide range of temperature.

Observation of data from Table 3 viz. the mesophase region and the heat of transition, it is very clear that these esters exhibit mesophase from or above 41–72 °C, except in case of compound (8), which show a second liquid crystal phase 138.35–161.65 °C. In case of compound (8) viz. the stearate ester, it is interesting to note that the compound required more heat of transition ΔH (149.3 j/g) for the phase during 56.0–71.6 °C, but the heat of transition decreases to lower value i.e. (12.7 j/g) during the second mesophase (138.5–161.61 °C). Another important thing is all the synthesized novel 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine (5–8) exhibited first mesophase at lower temperature. All the compounds are potential for further study to explore room temperature liquid crystals, which are aimed for industrial applications.

We are also carried out X-ray diffraction studies to 2,4,6-tri(*p*-palmitoyloxyphenyl)pyridine (7) for detection of columnar mesophase. The X-ray diffraction of compound (7) shows, the *d*-spacing of the three sharp peaks were in the ratio 1 : $1/\sqrt{3}$: 1/2. These values correspond to that expected from a two dimensional hexagonal lattice. The *d*-spacing values of first three intensive peaks of were 17.9 Å, 10.01 Å and 8.6 Å respectively. In the wide angle region there were two diffused peaks; a broad one at 19.8° and another relatively narrow peak at higher angles. The broad peak with a *d*-spacing of 4.4 Å was due to the liquid-like packing of the aliphatic chains. The relatively narrow peak, which was separated from the broader one, corresponds to a spacing of 3.56 Å and was due to core-to-core (intra columnar) separation. All the

features the hexagonal columnar (Col_h) phase, in which the disc-like molecules stack one on top of another to form columns, and the columns in turn are arranged in a two-dimensional hexagonal lattice.

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Kanithi *et al.* : Synthesis and mesophase characterization of novel 2,4,6-tri(*p*-acyloxyphenyl)pyridine *etc.*

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